

Novel multimodal approach of LA-ICP-MS exploring innovative Ru-tetrazene: In situ tracking and bioimaging-guided cancer treatment

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Fast-screening of anticancer Ru-tetrazene efficacy by single cell LA-ICP-MS analysis.
- Tracing label-free anticancer agent at femtogram level in cancer cell line.
- Multielement imaging of essential metals and Ru-tetrazene by sequential analyser.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

In this study, we employed LA-ICP-MS to trace a novel, unique Ru-based complex in a lung cancer cell line. This work highlights the importance of the time synchronization of all instrumentation, including the Aerosol Rapid Introduction System. It introduces bulk *in situ* LA-ICP-MS for rapid screening of chemotherapeutic penetration into the cell and the use of high-resolution 2D single cell imaging, which is used for both large-scale mapping for the monitoring of large cellular variability and for imaging single cells for the precise localization of ruthenium tetrazene accumulation. Furthermore, laser ablation sampling was employed to clarify the mechanism of the kinetics, with Ru-based substance cell influx determined after 6, 12 and 24 h of treatment with the complex. A pilot study employing multielement 2D imaging with Q-based ICP-MS was also conducted, in which the objects of interest were nutritional trace elements whose activity is directly related to the resistance mechanisms of cancer cells.

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Our results provide essential information about the broad-scale significance of the LA-ICP-MS technique in cancer research, including elucidating treatment efficacy, investigating the synergistic effects of various compounds during treatment and revealing kinetic and resistance mechanisms. These crucial steps towards personalised treatment are demonstrated using novel tetrazene. LA-ICP-MS, which focuses on tracing metals, metalloids and organometallic compounds, has strong potential for implementation in clinical research.

1. Introduction

Cancer is a diverse set of insidious diseases with tumour formation and aggressive malignancies causing millions of deaths worldwide each year [1]. The number of cancer patients is growing every year, and although research suggests that a personalised and targeted approach could be the future in oncology, conventional chemotherapy still forms the backbone of cancer treatment. The great chemotherapeutic potential for metal-based agents has been known for platinum derivatives [2]. However, conventional chemotherapeutic Pt derivatives [3–5] suffer from poor selectivity, resulting in damage to healthy tissue followed by the development of many negative side effects, and from low efficacy, leading to the use of large doses [6].

Therefore, when designing new anticancer agents, the emphasis is put on selectivity and effectiveness. In the last few decades, many researchers have focused on the synthesis of metal-based compounds replacing platinum with silver, bismuth, iron [7], zinc, gold and copper [8], or osmium, cobalt, rhodium [9], iridium [10] and ruthenium [11–13]. From the perspective of selectivity, the use of metals can be advantageous, as the central metal atom can be reduced to the active form of the compound only at the site of the required effect due to the hypoxic environment of tumours [14]. The metal core is usually also coordinated to individual ligands, which often provide the agent with various subsidiary functions, such as aiding drug penetration into cells and binding to specific targets, etc. Also, complexes whose primary function is antimetastatic are being examined.

With regard to investigating the defence mechanisms of cancer cells against conventional chemotherapeutics and potential anti-cancer compounds, as well as to elucidating the initiation, progression, and metastasis of cancer, metalloproteins are currently in the spotlight [15, 16]. The crucial trace elements in metalloproteins, such as iron, selenium, zinc and copper, play several vital roles in the organism [15,17]. Their dysregulation of their levels may be implicated in the development of a number of diseases and/or may be caused by the altered metabolism of damaged cells including changes in the need for trace elements, especially in cancer. Zinc deficiency can reduce the organism's ability to defend itself against cancer cells [18], as zinc's anti-tumour activity involves DNA repair or reducing oxidative stress, and zinc deficiency also corresponds to the size and stage of the tumour [17]. Conversely, elevated copper levels lead to cancer development and progression [15], where it is essential for tumour growth as a regulator of signal transduction and gene expression. Moreover, the transmembrane copper homeostasis-related protein copper transporter 1 (CTRL1) is of considerable importance in drug uptake [19]. Research into nutritional elements in the context of cancer brings us closer to a future in which it will be possible to 'reprogram' cancer cells and develop tailored-made treatments for each patient.

The identification, characterization and quantification of organo-metallic compounds and elucidation of their interactions with biomolecules are necessary for successful treatment strategies, and it is essential to incorporate cutting-edge advanced analytical techniques. These techniques must be capable of single-cell analysis as well as *in situ* imaging of the distribution of a potential medicament within cells, as only such information can help to fill current gaps in our understanding of the processes of drug delivery, cellular uptake, and processing in cells, including anticancer activity and targeting at the molecular level. Such techniques will thus play a unique role in improving the agent-development process [20]. Other essential requirements for single-cell

analysis techniques are low detection limits, high sensitivity, and the achievement of high spatial resolution for imaging cellular material, as well as the capacity for multielement analysis. In the last decade, a number of powerful analytical tools from the biospeciation toolbox have come to the fore. Synchrotron Radiation-Based X-ray Fluorescence [21, 22], Synchrotron X-ray Fluorescence Microscopy [23,24], Proton Induced X-ray Emission [25,26] and Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry [27,28] have been used in the past in the context of soft tissues or the 2D imaging of cells. Currently, the gold standard in inorganic investigation is Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry coupled with Laser Ablation sampling (LA-ICP-MS), which is now gaining prominence as a method for the *in situ* imaging of biological materials. Its undisputed advantages are its simplicity, cost, ability to detect a wide range of elements, high sensitivity, low limits of detection, rapid response, and sufficient spatial resolution.

The application of LA-ICP-MS has been verified in the study of neurodegenerative diseases [29] and in the localization of conventional platinum-, clinically tested ruthenium-, and slightly-modified osmium-based drugs in organs and tumours of mice or other animals after treatment [30,31]. In rare cases, the association of essential trace elements linked to cancer progression or response to treatment in human cancer tissues has also been recently investigated [32,33]. The rapid progress of instrumentation has led to a significant increase in spatial resolution and enhanced response allowing the tracking of ultra-trace amounts of analyte at femtogram levels [34–36]. The pilot studies of single cell analysis by LA-ICP-MS are now starting to emerge. However, in most cases, labelling with silver or gold nanoparticles [37,38], or with high concentrations of metal tags or rare earth element-based probes [39] for antibody detection eliminate the risk of undetectability. Moreover, it can help to recognize the target protein specifically through an immune response [40–42]. In addition to the use of labelling, studies have mostly focused on animal material; hence, there is a lack of studies on the monitoring of unlabelled metallodrugs in ultra-trace amounts quantities taken up by human cells; furthermore, the link between metalloproteins and chemotherapeutic agents at the single cell level has not been investigated by LA-ICP-MS.

Multielement analysis, i.e. the determination of multiple isotopes within a single *in situ* LA-ICP-MS measurement, is also challenging, as it is usually limited by the scanning speed of the mass analyser [42]. Sequential mass analysers do not fully support the measurement of multiple elements within a single event, and if multiple isotopes need to be imaged, the dwell time for each analyte isotope must be optimized to achieve the desired detection limits [36]. For this type of analysis, it would obviously be preferable to choose a dynamic time-of-flight (TOF) analyser [43,44]. Nevertheless, TOF analysers are more costly and therefore not as widespread in conventional laboratory workplaces as sequential quadrupole analysers (Q-MS), which are nowadays increasingly used in 2D imaging. In this type of analysis, the sample is continuously scanned, i.e. a dynamic ablative line scan mode is used, which produces a continuous mass flow, however sequential mass spectrometry response. Due to the frequent use of Q-MS and taking into account their limitations, it is necessary to develop a suitable methodology for multielement 2D analysis.

The present study deals with the investigation of the possibilities and significance of using the LA-ICP-MS method in oncological research. The main focus is on the scope of information portfolio to be extracted by the application of LA-ICP-MS. It is presented with using a completely unique non-labelled ruthenium tetrazene and the impact of differences in

Fig. 1. The structure of the ruthenium tetrazene complex.

harvesting times after treatment of cancer cells with this tetrazene complex. The study thus investigates a) fast-screening *in situ* bulk analysis by single cell LA-ICP-MS analysis, b) the application of high-resolution 2D bioimaging to label-free cell lines for large-format mapping to monitor high variability, and for small-format mapping to monitor the detailed localization of ruthenium complex accumulation, and c) the potential of sequential Q-MS for multielement analysis to explore the involvement of nutritional elements in cancer mechanisms, and to elucidate certain metabolic processes in order to improve the prognosis and treatment of cancer.

2. Experimental

2.1. Cultivation and preparation of cells for solution nebulization ICP-MS analysis

All experiments were performed on the human alveolar basal cell adenocarcinoma cell line A549. The cell line was cultured in DMEM medium (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Federal Republic of Germany) supplemented with 10 % (v/v) FBS (foetal bovine serum; Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc, Waltham, Massachusetts, USA), 2 mmol/l pyruvate (Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Inc., Waltham, Massachusetts, USA), 100 U/ml penicillin, and 100 µg/ml streptomycin (SERANA, Pessin, Federal Republic of Germany). Cells were cultured in a humidity-controlled incubator at 37 °C in a 5 % (v/v) CO₂ atmosphere. Cells passaged a maximum of 20 times were used for the experiment. Subsequent cell preparation was performed separately for laser ablation (tens of thousands of cells) and solution analysis (millions of cells).

To prepare pellets for solution analysis, the cell line was cultured in 10-ml culture dishes (TPP Techno Plastic Products AG, Trasadingen, Switzerland) at 60 % confluence. The tested ruthenium tetrazene complex ($[\eta^5\text{-}(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)\text{RuCl-1,4-}\kappa^2\text{-N}_2\text{N}'\text{-(1,4-bis(2,3,4,6-tetra-O-acetyl-}\beta\text{-D-glucopyranosyl)tetrazene)]$) (Fig. 1) was prepared at the Institute of Chemical Process Fundamentals of the Czech Academy of Sciences in collaboration with J. Heyrovský Institute of Physical Chemistry of the Czech Academy of Sciences in 2020. The synthesis of this ruthenium tetrazene complex has been reported in our previous study [45]. The ruthenium tetrazene complex contains an attached glucose moiety, which enabled to modulate the lipophilicity of the entire complex by O-acylation. The O-acetylated ruthenium tetrazene showed high single-digit micromolar cytotoxicity to cancer cell lines A2780, SK-OV-3, and noncancerous cell line HEK-293 [45]. We hypothesized that the high cytotoxicity of this complex is associated with its higher lipophilicity and easier penetration into cells by passive diffusion. This motivated us to investigate the biodistribution of ruthenium in cells treated with this ruthenium tetrazene complex.

5×10^5 cells were seeded into 10-ml plates. After 24 h, a ruthenium tetrazene compound dissolved in DMSO (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Federal Republic of Germany) was added to the cells at a final concentration of 10 µmol/l. Cells treated with DMSO alone served as a control samples.

At each time point (6, 12, and 24 h), the residual culture medium was aspirated from the plates, and the cells were rinsed with $1 \times$ PBS (0.14 mol/l NaCl (Lach-Ner, s. r.o., Neratovice, Czech Republic), 2.68 mmol/l KCl (Lach-Ner, s. r.o., Neratovice, Czech Republic), 1.47 mmol/l

KH₂PO₄ (Lach-Ner, s. r.o., Neratovice, Czech Republic), and 7.68 mmol/l Na₂HPO₄ (Lach-Ner, s. r.o., Neratovice, Czech Republic). Cells were subsequently harvested using trypsin (Gold Biotechnology, St. Louis, Missouri, USA). Before centrifugation, cells were counted on a CASY model TT flow cytometer. Then, the cell suspensions were spun down for 10 min at 1000 g and 4 °C. The resulting pellets were stored at -80 °C until further processing.

2.2. Preparation of cell lines for LA-ICP-MS analysis

Glass slides with a diameter of 12 mm (P-LAB, Prague, Czech Republic) were stored in 70 % (v/v) ethanol and illuminated with UV light for 30 min before use. The first day, the slides were placed in 12-well plates (TPP Techno Plastic Products AG, Trasadingen, Switzerland) into which cells were subsequently seeded at a density of 30,000 cells/well. Cultivation of the A549 cell line and treatment with ruthenium complex was performed in the same manner as for bulk analysis. The culture medium was aspirated after 6, 12 and 24 h and the cells and slides were rinsed with 1x PBS. Subsequently 0.5 ml of a pre-cooled mixture of methanol and acetone (1:1 (v/v)) stored at -20 °C was pipetted into each well of the plate. The fixative mixture was left on the cells for 6 min at room temperature. Thereafter, the slides were removed from the wells and placed onto pulp to air-dry for 1 h. Finally, the slides containing fixed cells were placed in new clean 12-well plates and stored at -80 °C.

2.3. Mineralization of cells

Mineralization of the samples to determine the average Ru content in the A549 cells was performed using an ultraWAVE microwave device (Milestone Srl, Italy). Pellet samples were moved from Eppendorf microtubes to quartz tubes and weighed on analytical balances with a precision to 0.01 mg. The weights of cell pellets subjected to mineralization ranged from 6.20 to 11.86 mg. The cells were mineralized using 100 µl of 65 % sub-boiled HNO₃.

The initial pressure of the inert atmosphere of the reactor during cell decomposition was 40 bar. The setting of the instrument did not allow the maximum pressure value to exceed 110 bar. The temperature was ramped over 15 min to 220 °C, where it was maintained for 10 min. The total time per decomposition cycle including cooling was approximately 35 min. This procedure yielded a mineralizate, which was diluted by 1 ml of deionised water.

2.4. Solution nebulizer ICP-MS analysis

An Agilent 7900 ICP-MS quadrupole ICP mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Inc., USA) in conjunction with an SPS 4 autosampler (Agilent Technologies, Inc., USA) was used to analyse the average Ru content in the cell mineralizates. Optimization was carried out while monitoring $^7\text{Li}^+$, $^{87}\text{Y}^+$, $^{205}\text{Tl}^+$, and $^{140}\text{Ce}^+$ to achieve maximal signal intensities. Plasma robustness was checked via the $^{140}\text{Ce}^{2+}/^{140}\text{Ce}^+$ and $^{140}\text{Ce}^{16}\text{O}^+/^{140}\text{Ce}^+$ intensity ratios, the ratio intensity values in both cases being less than 5 %. The quantification was established using external calibration with a set of calibration solutions containing an increased amount of ruthenium. The calibration solutions were prepared using a certified reference material – mix of seven elements (Au, Ir, Os, Pd, Pt, Rh and Ru at a concentration of 100 ± 0.2 mg/L), part number: AN9087MC-100, Analytical s. r.o., Czech Republic. Calculations were performed using the regression equation $y = ax + b$. The detection limit was calculated by the instrument from the calibration dependence according to the formula $\text{LOD} = \frac{3 \cdot \text{SD}_b}{a}$, where SD_b represents the standard deviation of the count at the zero-concentration level and a is the slope from the linear equation. The resulting LOD values corresponded to $\text{LOD} (^{101}\text{Ru}^+) = 4.05$ ng/l.

For the solution nebulizer (SN) ICP-MS analysis itself, the final

Table 1
SN-ICP-MS working parameters.

ICP-MS parameters	
Analysed isotopes	$^{101}\text{Ru}^+$
Integration time (ms)	100
RF power (W)	1550
Sample depth (mm)	8.0
Nebulizer gas (l/min)	1.03
$^{140}\text{Ce}^{2+}/^{140}\text{Ce}^+$	0.79 %
$^{140}\text{Ce}^{16}\text{O}^+/^{140}\text{Ce}^+$	0.96 %

Table 2
LA-ICP-MS working parameters for bulk analysis, 2D imaging of $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ and 2D multielemental imaging.

ICP-MS parameter	<i>In situ</i> bulk analysis	2D imaging	2D multielemental imaging	NIST 610
Analysed isotopes	$^{101}\text{Ru}^+$		$^{63}\text{Cu}^+$, $^{66}\text{Zn}^+$, $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$	$^{28}\text{Si}^+$, $^{85}\text{Rb}^+$
Integration time (ms)	30		90, 90, 90	30, 10
RF power (W)	1550			
Sample depth (mm)	5.5			
Nebulizer gas (l/min)	~0.85			
LA parameter	<i>In situ</i> bulk analysis	2D imaging	2D multielemental imaging	NIST 610
Ablation mode	spot analysis	line scan	line of spots	line scan
Spot size (μm)	25	2	2	2
Fluence (J/cm^2)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Scan speed ($\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$)	–	50	–	16.5
Shot count (–)	5	–	5	–
Rap rate (Hz)	50	50	50	50
Line distance (μm)	–	2	2	4
Spot distance (μm)	–	–	2	–
Line length (μm)	–	750	85	400
Number of lines (–)	–	375	43	100
He low rate	0.6			
MC1+MC2 (l/min)				

parameters of the analysed $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope are listed in Table 1.

2.5. LA-ICP-MS analysis

To localize the complex accumulation or its adducts in the cell, laser ablation was employed as a sampling method coupled to ICP-MS. LA-ICP-MS analysis was performed using the Analyte Excite + laser ablation system (Teledyne CETAC Technologies, USA), an ArF* excimer ablation system emitting radiation at 193 nm with a pulse length <4 ns, and the Aerosol Rapid Introduction System (ARIS; Teledyne CETAC Technologies, USA). The LA-ICP-MS was tuned using the standard reference glass material (SRM) NIST 612 to monitor ion intensity and to minimize oxide and doubly-charged ion formation.

The fast screening of ruthenium complex levels in cells via bulk *in situ* analysis was performed using LA-ICP-MS, where 40 cells were analysed separately for each sample. The diameter of the laser beam was increased to 25 μm to ensure that the entire cell surface in the x and y axes was always ablated (average cell size approximately 18 μm). At the same time, the dose was set to 5 laser pulses per point to ensure complete ablation in the z-axis.

For 2D imaging of a larger sample area, and thus for the analysis of a

Fig. 2. Box plot analysis of the average composition of samples with different times of cell treatment.

larger number of cells, the dynamic ablation line scan mode was chosen. An important consideration in the monitoring of ruthenium tetrazene distribution within a single cell is to achieve as high a spatial resolution as possible. Therefore, the beam diameter was set to 2 μm . The scan speed was adjusted in dependence on a frequency of 50 Hz [40], and, finally, the higher value of the scan rate was chosen – specifically, 50 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$. To sputter whole cellular material, and concurrently to avoid ablation of the glass substrate, the sampling was achieved with 2.5 J/cm^2 fluence.

To study the precise localization of the ruthenium complex within the cellular system using 2D imaging, a smaller area containing 3–5 cells was also ablated, with the emphasis on visualizing ruthenium within a single cell, using the ablative mode of spot analysis employing a line of spots pattern.

To investigate the correlation between the distribution of the ruthenium tetrazene and the essential elements copper and zinc in cancer cells. Due to the need for slower material sputtering in multi-elemental sequence detection Q-MS, a lower scan speed of 17 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ was chosen.

The SRM NIST 610 was analysed simultaneously with the sample to correct for instrumental drift and instrument sensitivity changes. The set-up conditions for the laser ablation system had to be adjusted for NIST 610; due to the variability in the homogeneity of this material, the laser beam diameter was increased [46]. Due to the absence of ruthenium in NIST 610, the signal response of the $^{85}\text{Rb}^+$ isotope and $^{28}\text{Si}^+$ was monitored, since NIST is a glass material. The resulting parameters for all LA-ICP-MS experiments, *in situ* bulk analysis, and 2D imaging, including multielement determination, are shown in Table 2.

The HDF-based image processing software HDIP (Teledyne Photon Machines Inc., Bozeman, MT, USA) was used to evaluate all data acquired by LA-ICP-MS. In the case of spot analysis, the resulting signal peak areas corresponding to the ablated cells were integrated using HDIP software after background correction, and these values were corrected to the cell area, which was calculated approximately from the diameter of each cell by assuming a circular shape. To evaluate the 2D data, the same software was used to visualize the results when the isotope images were reconstructed.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. *In situ* bulk analysis via LA-ICP-MS

Due to the need for a dose-response characteristic, the efficient screening of ruthenium compound kinetics and its levels in cells was performed using *in situ* bulk LA-ICP-MS analysis. The advantage of this

Table 3
Average amount of Ru per cell exposed to ruthenium tetrazene, harvested at different time intervals.

Sample	Ru content (fg/cell)
Control	<2.6
6 h after treatment	454 ± 15 ^a
12 h after treatment	234.6 ± 9.6 ^a
24 h after treatment	254 ± 14 ^a

^a Standard deviations based on replicate sample measurements (n = 3).

method consists in the rapid screening of complex efficacy and the elimination of a mineralization step as in SN-ICP-MS. The experiment using the spot analysis mode of laser ablation was realized with 25 µm laser beam must be set to ablate the whole cell as the analysed material is in diameter of approximately 18 µm. As the bulk analysis determines the average response of ruthenium corresponding to the individual cell without rastering, each peak in the time-resolved signal relates to an individual cell. The analysed cell samples were placed on glass slides and collected at 6, 12 and 24 h of treatment of the cells with the complex. Individual cells were analysed under the working conditions for spot analysis (Table 2), with a laser beam size of 25 µm and 5 pulses to ablate the entire cell volume within a single spot. For each sample, 40 cells were sputtered. A control sample without treatment was also examined and no ¹⁰¹Ru⁺ isotope signal was detected. The resulting integrated peak areas corrected for cell area are summarized in Fig. 2.

The results from cells collected after 6 h provide a dataset with asymmetry, where most of the data is concentrated in the lower values; however, there are some extremely high values that increase the average. The difference between the median value equal to 83 (illustrated by the horizontal line inside the box) and the mean value 93 confirms the asymmetric distribution of the data. Moreover, the large interquartile range suggests considerable variability. The data corresponding to the 12-h treatment are more consistent, providing a data set with a symmetric distribution and a distribution around a midpoint value of 129. The large interquartile range indicates considerable variability in the data, but consistency across the entire data set. The results of the 24-h treatment show data with significant right asymmetry and large variability. Most of the data are concentrated in the lower values around a median of 78, which is significantly lower compared to the mean value of 104.

According to the response-dose characteristic, it can be assumed that after ruthenium tetrazene administration, cellular influx occurs, represented by a sample harvested after 6 h with considerable system variability. The cell sample after the 12-h treatment most likely represents the equilibrium of the system; i.e., the saturation of the cells and the beginning of the efflux, which is in a good agreement with the symmetric distribution of the data. After 24 h, the values are at the same level as those for the sample after 6 h. Thus, it can be expected that cellular efflux predominates, as indicated by the large variability of the system. Variation within individual samples and in cellular uptake and efflux might be due to differences in cell design as well as cell transformation after 24-h exposure and an increase in the number of non-viable cells with the original amount of ruthenium complex. These cells are no longer subject to influx or efflux.

The average composition is often determined using solution ICP-MS analysis after mineralization of the cell pellets. Therefore, this approach was also used to compare the LA-ICP-MS results (Table 3).

The results of the solution analysis of the cell pellets after mineralization showed that the ruthenium level in the control sample was below the detection limit, which was calculated from the calibration dependence of 2.6 fg per cell. This is in agreement with the results of the LA-ICP-MS analysis. The highest ruthenium accumulation was identified after the 6-h treatment. Approximately two times lower levels were found in cell samples collected 12 and 24 h after treatment. Although the

ruthenium contents in these two samples do not overlap when standard deviations are taken into account, the standard deviations in the case of SN-ICP-MS represent only variations in measurement.

SN-ICP-MS did not fully confirm the trend of *in situ* bulk LA-ICP-MS analysis. The discrepancy could be caused by the different cell numbers used in the preparations for SN (millions of cells per pellet) versus LA (30,000 cells per glass, 40 cells analysed) analysis. The laser ablation results show a higher amount of Ru in cells with a 12-h treatment, and a similar response with 6-h and 24-h treatments. Furthermore, the bulk *in situ* analysis exhibits larger scattered values than the standard deviations of the solution analysis presented in Table 3. The standard deviations of the solution analysis are calculated from repeated measurements of a single replicate sample, whereas the scatter of the laser ablation results corresponds to the variability of individual cells. Another discrepancy between LA and solution analysis is the process of sample processing. In the case of solution analysis, the cells were spun down into an Eppendorf vessel containing a known number of cells, which were counted using a cytometer. Subsequently, the cell suspension with the known concentration of cells must be transferred into the reaction vessels of the digestion system by pipetting, in order to replace the maximum original number of cells. The final number of cells to be digested is calculated proportionally according to the sample weight. During this process, errors can be caused by an unknown exact weight of the residual medium in the cell suspension, as the total weight is attributed to the cells only. However, we suppose that the main reason for the slightly different results of LA and SN relates to working with a completely different number of cells: digestion and solution analysis of millions of cells versus 40 cells analysed by LA-ICP-MS. The different cell numbers could result in different levels of ruthenium complex availability to the cells themselves. Moreover, the laser ablation is burdened with manifestation of the high variability of cells more than solution analysis ICP-MS. The results could be comparable only if more than 40 cells are investigated.

Although it is not possible to define the maximum content for a specific treatment time using significance statistics due to high scattering, *in situ* bulk analysis can be used to differentiate between cells based on their cargo, or to determine the efficacy of treatments involving different types of compounds, where greater differences in influx are expected.

3.2. 2D imaging by line scanning mode

In addition to *in situ* bulk analysis, large-scale 2D cell mapping for rapid localization was performed. Localization is essential for evaluating treatment interactions, such as whether it reaches the nuclei or accumulates in the intracellular space. It requires to achieve as high spatial resolution as possible, therefore, the beam diameter was set to 2 µm. The samples were sputtered in line scanning mode; however the drawback of that dynamic sampling mode is the overlapping of ablation craters depending on the scan speed and frequency. On the other hand, a suitable choice of parameters leads to a smaller depth of the ablated trace. The scan speed 50 µm/s settings in combination with a frequency of 50 Hz resulted in a resolution of 1 laser pulse for each 1 µm. The goal was to ablate, in a single analysis, as many cells as possible with respect to monitoring variability in ruthenium tetrazene levels as a function of cellular influx. For the purpose of high-resolution 2D imaging, it was necessary to synchronize the laser ablation system with the mass spectrometer, as the introduced Aerosol Rapid Introduction System (ARIS) enables a lower washout time than the conventional HelEx II ablation cell. These devices together allow the entire ablation cell volume to be washed out in the order of units to tens of milliseconds (<20 ms [47]), whereas without ARIS, the washout would take higher hundreds of milliseconds (≈700 ms, [48]). Rapid cell washout has many advantages, primarily related to improved spatial resolution, and thus results in a narrow peak corresponding to the aerosol from a single laser pulse with no gradual peak smearing. The fast washout also minimizes aerosol mixing between pulses, allowing detection of individual ablation events

Fig. 3. Time-resolved $^{85}\text{Rb}^+$ signal in NIST 610 at various integration times: a) 100 ms, b) 30 ms, c) 10 ms, and d) 3 ms.

by the mass spectrometer. The signals are also more “concentrated” in time, i.e., they are characterized by higher peak intensities and lead to an improved signal-to-noise ratio in ICP-MS [49]. Proper synchronization of the laser ablation system with the mass spectrometer is crucial for obtaining correct information on the composition of the aerosol. In this context, a detailed study of the effect of the integration time (IT) of the monitored isotope on the time-resolved ICP-MS response was performed.

The study of the integration time effect was first performed on the A549 cell model, where the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope was monitored under the line scan conditions shown in Table 2. Due to the huge variability of the living system, no reproducible trend with decreasing integration time during cell ablation was demonstrated. The increase and/or decrease in intensity values were more related to the analyte content in the individual cells as well as to their design, such as their size and topography, rather than to the change in integration time itself.

Therefore, the investigation was subsequently performed on NIST 610 standard reference material and the response to $^{85}\text{Rb}^+$ was monitored due to the absence of ruthenium in the reference material. Rubidium is in NIST 610 at the relatively high content of 425.7 $\mu\text{g/g}$ [50]. The setup conditions for NIST 610 laser ablation were modified due to the different physicochemical properties compared to cellular material, including a higher threshold energy required to achieve ablation; thus, the fluence was increased to 3 J/cm^2 [51]. In addition, due to the variability in the homogeneity of this material [46], the laser beam diameter was increased to 8 μm . The final and important parameters influencing the laser ablation process were retained – specifically, a 50 Hz frequency and a 50 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ scan speed. The effect was monitored in the ablation mode of the line scan for integration times ranging from 100 to 10 ms in steps of 10 ms, and 3 ms. The time-resolved signals obtained by the ablation of a single line of 80 μm in length give different waveforms depending on the value of the integration time, Fig. 3.

The $^{85}\text{Rb}^+$ isotope signal is stable from 100 ms, when the analysed aerosol is highly mixed. Even at the lower integration time of 20 ms, a relatively stable signal is achieved, but it displays more fluctuations and the number of points rendering the time-resolved signal increases. A completely different signal behaviour is visible at an IT of 10 ms, when

the signal oscillates around a mean value with gradually increasing and then decreasing intensity, resulting in a specific signal clustering structure. This is probably caused by the resynchronisation of the LA washout and ICP-MS detection. In contrast, an IT equal to 3 ms shows that the signal drops to background level every 20 ms. The total number of maxima is equal to 80, which corresponds to the number of pulses required to ablate an 80- μm length line at a scan speed of 50 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ and a frequency of 50 Hz. Thus, it can be concluded that under the given experimental conditions and using ARIS, it is possible to determine the aerosol composition from each laser pulse. A noticeable difference is also the change in the intensities achieved. Within the course of the time-resolved signal from 100 ms to 20 ms, the achieved intensity values range from 9.0×10^4 – 10^5 cps. Up to 10 ms, due to signal oscillation, the maximum achieved intensities are observed to reach above 1.5×10^5 cps and within the lowest integration time, to reach almost 3.0×10^5 cps. This would suggest that despite the rapid washout and analysis of material from a single laser pulse, the resolution of ICP-MS is enhanced.

In a study of the synchronization of a laser ablation system with ARIS and a quadrupole mass spectrometer, it was shown that by reducing the integration time to units of ms, an excellent and fast washout of the aerosol obtained by the ablation of homogeneous NIST 610 material containing high levels of $^{85}\text{Rb}^+$ analyte is achieved.

However, the use of this integration time for 2D mapping is limited by the length of the analysis in terms of the computational capabilities of the Q-based ICP mass spectrometer. The ICP mass spectrometer is typically capable of processing only a limited volume of data at an IT of 3 ms, corresponding to approximately 25 min of measurement time. For these reasons, the IT value for the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope was set to 30 ms. It was experimentally verified that at this IT no beats formation in the time resolved signal occurs and that detailed cell rendering is achieved. In this way, it is possible to localize elements in small cellular compartments.

The aim of this part of the experiment was to rapidly localize the ruthenium complex using large-format 2D imaging while investigating cellular influx, efflux and cell saturation, i.e. to determine the overall kinetics of ruthenium tetrazene in the cellular compartment by means of LA-ICP-MS. The individual cell samples differed in the time of Ru-

Fig. 4. Images of the analysed area from the CCD camera of the laser ablation system (left) and the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope distribution map (right) obtained by linear ablation of the A549 cell line after treatment with ruthenium tetrazene with a harvesting interval of a) 6 h, b) 12 h, c) 24 h. The scale bars placed in imaging maps correspond to the CCD images.

compound exposure – specifically, 6, 12 and 24 h. The fitted parameters (Table 2) allowed an area of $750 \times 750 \mu\text{m}$ containing approximately 150 cells to be investigated, and thus the variability of the living system to be studied in a single analysis, Fig. 4. A control sample that was not treated with the ruthenium complex was also analysed along with the samples. It was verified that no $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ signal was detected in the control sample (not shown).

In Fig. 4, for all cell collections at time intervals of 6, 12 and 24 h of ruthenium tetrazene treatment, the localization of the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope in the cells as well as in the vicinity of cells is clearly defined.

In all the cells located in the analysed area after 6-h treatment in Fig. 4 a), ruthenium, and therefore the complex or its adducts or metabolites, were present in different levels. Due to the absence of ruthenium in the SRM, it was not possible to quantify these abundances

Fig. 5. Images of the analysed area taken by the CCD camera of the laser ablation system (left) and the distribution maps of the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope (right) in the A549 cell line after 6-h treatment obtained by spot analysis. The scale bars placed in imaging maps correspond to the CCD images.

Fig. 6. Images of the analysed area taken by the CCD camera of the laser ablation system (left) and the distribution maps of the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope (right) in the A549 cell line after 12-h treatment obtained by spot analysis. The scale bars placed in imaging maps correspond to the CCD images.

Fig. 7. Images of the analysed area taken by the CCD camera of the laser ablation system (left) and the distribution maps of the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope (right) in the A549 cell line after 24-h treatment obtained by spot analysis. The scale bars placed in imaging maps correspond to the CCD images.

Fig. 8. Images of the analysed areas from the CCD camera of the laser ablation system of a A549 cell line samples after 6h-, 12h- and 24h-treatment with ruthenium tetrazena and isotope distribution maps of $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$, $^{66}\text{Zn}^+$ and $^{63}\text{Cu}^+$ isotopes obtained by line scan ablation.

proportionally; however, the results can at least be compared as a function of the intensities achieved, where the highest $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope intensities after background correction were around 200–180 cts. With respect to the ruthenium distribution after 12-h treatment (Fig. 4 b), individual cells were clearly distinguished again, with a much more cellular structure in their surroundings than the cells in the previous case. In contrast to the previous distribution map, a greater accumulation of ruthenium tetrazena in the cells was achieved after 12 h, as the highest intensity values after background correction were around 300 cts. Higher intensities compared to the 6-h treatment sample correlate with the results of *in situ* bulk analysis and support the hypothesis of ongoing cellular influx. On the other hand, greater variability in the system is evident compared to the sample 6 h after treatment. Only 5–10 % of the total number of cells analysed achieved the highest intensities,

but the increase in the intensity scale resulted in a gradual rendering of the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope distribution in cells towards lower levels. The last sample analysed was harvested after 24 h of treatment and corresponded to the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope distribution, (Fig. 4 c), showing the lowest maximum intensities (~80 cts) achieved compared to the previous samples. The decrease in the obtained intensities again fitted the trend shown by the bulk analysis via LA-ICP-MS. Twelve hours after ruthenium tetrazena application, the cellular influx of the complex predominantly occurred, because the maximum intensities were reached, while between 12 and 24 h, the rate of efflux outweighed the influx rate, causing the signal to decrease. Fig. 4 also demonstrates the feasibility of using LA-ICP-MS to rapidly assess treatment efficacy. The randomly selected analysed area includes a higher number of cells (approximately 125 in this study), which reflects the results of the SN-ICP-MS analysis

(Table 3).

The distribution maps of all samples show that the distribution of the complex within the studied cells was not completely constant. The amount of ruthenium complex present in a cell may depend on the morphological properties of the cell, but information about the cell topography is not available. Cells where higher intensities were achieved may have been more convex and therefore more cellular material will have been ablated by the laser beam. In addition, the amount of ruthenium tetrazene absorbed could also depend on the state of the cell. Comparison of the images of the analysed areas shows the morphological changes in the cells at different sampling times after treatment. These morphological changes could be due to the response of the cells to the complex, either related to resistance mechanisms or the induction of apoptosis. All maps show ruthenium deposition in specific locations. Most likely, these are nuclei, but due to the large map area, it is not possible to make a definitive statement.

When analysing larger areas, it was found that the values of the working parameters using line scanning mode were set appropriately, and thus an efficient and rapid methodology was developed for the ultra-trace analysis of large numbers of cells with ruthenium-based complex ranging in the hundreds of fg per cell without the use of labelling. The distribution maps show that ruthenium tetrazene or its adducts were deposited in the cells, and at specific sites. For this reason, the 2D imaging of smaller regions subsequently resorted to the use of spot analysis to better visualize the distribution of $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ within a single cell.

3.3. 2D imaging by spot analysis

Spot analysis mode with a “line of spots” pattern was used to show the detailed distribution of Ru-complex through the cell and to identify specific locations in cells where this compound accumulated. Spot analysis ablates precisely defined areas without overlapping, unlike line scanning. As in the case of *in situ* bulk analysis, the number of pulses applied to one spot was set to 5. The other working parameters are summarized in Table 2.

2D imaging by spot analysis was performed with the same cell samples as in the previous experiments. For each sample, three areas of $(85 \times 86) \mu\text{m}$ containing 3–5 cells of size 10–18 μm were selected to partially include the variability of the living system. The resulting $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ distribution maps for each sample are shown in Figs. 5–7.

The $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ distribution maps accurately define the locations with the highest ruthenium levels within a single cell and also characterize the vicinity of cells. The ranges of intensities of all distribution maps show great biological variability. When averaging the highest intensities achieved, the highest levels of ruthenium were again reached in the case of cell samples after 12-h treatment, which is consistent with the results obtained from *in situ* bulk analysis and 2D imaging by line scan laser ablation, and with the trend of cell saturation with the compound and incipient efflux.

For all three samples, the distribution maps of the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope reveal that not all cells contained similar amounts of ruthenium. The uptake of ruthenium by cells is most likely influenced by cell size and morphology.

In some cases, we can see confined regions inside cells marked with yellow arrows in Figs. 5 and 7. These limited structures are probably the nuclei of the cells. In some cases, higher levels of ruthenium are achieved in these confined regions, suggesting that ruthenium tetrazene could reach cell DNA as a therapeutic target. In other cases, more $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ is found just outside these confined cell regions. The interaction of ruthenium tetrazene with the cell can induce morphological changes in the cell, and these changes can influence the ongoing distribution of the ruthenium complex throughout the cellular system. To prove the localization, the compartments will have to be visualised by immunoassay.

When analysing smaller areas, it was verified that units of cells should be preferentially examined by spot 2D imaging, since the

sputtered aerosol from defined locations is precisely defined and not mixed. With appropriate parameter settings, a detailed visualization of the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ distribution within a single cell was performed and points out the accumulation probably in nucleus. The results also depend on the time of treatment, and thus reflect the state of the cell, its viability, and its morphology, as well as the kinetics of ruthenium tetrazene – specifically influx and efflux ratio.

3.4. Multielemental analysis using a sequential mass spectrometer

As mentioned in the introduction, zinc and copper are essential trace elements involved in key cellular processes, including redox regulation, proliferation, and apoptosis. Their dyshomeostasis contributes to the cancer development and progression. The zinc deficiency in the body corresponds to the size and stage of a tumour [17] while elevated level of copper impacts tumour progression by influencing angiogenesis, metastasis and other processes [15]. For this reason, a pilot study was conducted, the main challenge of which was multielement analysis using a sequential quadrupole mass spectrometer. The $^{63}\text{Cu}^+$ isotope detection was complicated due to a low signal-to-background ratio, caused by the lower copper levels in the cells. Considering this fact, the corresponding integration time for the detection of the $^{63}\text{Cu}^+$ isotope was set to 90 ms. On the contrary, both $^{66}\text{Zn}^+$ and $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotopes could be detected at lower IT than 90 ms, but to avoid subsequently distortion of images when using a sequential quadrupole MS, the integration times for all isotopes were set to 90 ms.

The resulting levels of $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ show the tetrazene influx in all treatments (Fig. 8). Moreover, the $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ isotope distributions are consistent with previous findings from *in situ* bulk laser ablation analysis; more ruthenium is present in cells in the 12h- and 24h-treatments. This may indicate preferential ongoing ruthenium tetrazene cellular influx up to approximately 12 h after complex administration and then persistent cellular uptake together with incipient efflux, up to 24 h after treatment.

Additionally, 2D multielement LA-ICP-MS analysis (Fig. 8) show that it is possible to detect levels of both copper and zinc in all samples at the set experimental parameters and cells are completely resolved despite the presumed low levels of these.

Within the sample treated for 6 h with ruthenium tetrazene, it is evident that there is a correlation between copper and zinc, while the levels of both elements in the cells are relatively low. In the case of $^{66}\text{Zn}^+$, the distribution maps show that the highest intensities were reached in the 12-h post-treatment sample, with a decrease in 24h-treatment samples, comparable to 6h-treatment. The comparison of $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ and $^{66}\text{Zn}^+$ levels exhibits the positive correlation between these elements. Based on this fact, the ruthenium tetrazene influx might cause the upregulation zinc-metalloproteins as part of a cellular stress or resistance response [17,52]. Conversely, significant $^{63}\text{Cu}^+$ accumulation correlates with 24-h treatment [15,53]. Therefore, it is possible that cells increase their demand for copper uptake with increased ruthenium tetrazene efflux, and thus copper protein upregulation can relate to higher resistance of cancer cells to chemotherapeutic [54]. Alternatively, the observed accumulation of copper at 24 h may also reflect the induction of copper-dependent cell death pathways driven by mitochondrial dysfunction or oxidative stress. Generally, the investigation of Zn and Cu distribution may characterize the influx/efflux kinetics of ruthenium tetrazene at various stages resistance mechanism or, alternatively, the activation of metal-induced cell death pathways.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we investigated the possibilities of using the LA-ICP-MS method in the field of medicine, specifically in oncological research. Our focus was on treating the A549 human lung cancer cell line with the completely unique non-labelled ruthenium structure and differences resulting from different harvest times after treatment.

This pioneering study demonstrates the utility of rapid *in situ* volumetric screening of anti-cancer agent efficacy using LA-ICP-MS single cell analysis. It eliminates the need for a mineralization step and indicates a possible trend in the cellular influx and efflux of ruthenium tetrazene after 6-, 12- and 24-h treatment. At the same time, it has been shown that it is necessary to analyse a larger number of cells to obtain representative information due to the inherent variability of cells.

Moreover, in the case of large-scale mapping, the LA-ICP-MS method provides the high-resolution 2D bioimaging of label-free cancer cells to study not only the cellular influx and efflux of anti-cancer compounds, but also the distribution of these compounds within the cell. Small-scale mapping with a spatial resolution of 2 μm using spot analysis can bring the information about therapeutic target within the cell compartments, as demonstrated by more precise localization of $^{101}\text{Ru}^+$ complex accumulation in cells.

Last but not least, the study demonstrates the potential of laser ablation coupled to sequential ICP-Q-MS in multielement analysis. The investigation into the distribution of the nutritional trace elements together with the anti-cancer compound can elucidate resistant mechanism of cancer cells and, thereby, can improve cancer diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment efficacy.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kristýna Bilavčíková: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Michaela Vašinová Galiová:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Roman Hrstka:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Vojtěch Hamala:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation. **Jindřich Karban:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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